

NORMAL AND SHEAR STRENGTH OF BIMATERIAL JOINTS USING MODIFIED GEOMETRIES OF THE TENSILE AND IOSIPESCU SPECIMENS

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Keywords: Adhesion strength, Iosipescu test, Stress singularities, Bimaterials, Composite material.

ABSTRACT

Failure prediction of adhesive joints between dissimilar materials using an approach of Finite Fracture Mechanics requires, among other mechanical properties, the knowledge of the tensile and shear strengths along the potential failure paths. Typical failures in adhesive joints include interface failures between the adherents and adhesive, these tensile and shear strengths being the objective of the present study. The main drawback of these strength determinations is that the bimaterial samples to be tested in tension and/or shear include bimaterial corners where the abrupt change in mechanical properties gives rise to stress singularities. The presence of such stress singularities makes the stress state strongly non-uniform and makes it difficult to determine the interface strength. In the present study two proposals for bimaterial samples tested in tension and shear are addressed. These samples include small notches at the free edge of the bimaterial corners avoiding the stress singularities to appear. These modifications have been performed both in the tensile and Iosipescu samples. Numerical models are performed to assess the vanishing of the stresses at these points and experimental test are done. Test results show a clear influence of these notches in the tensile samples but no significant influence is observed in the shear tests using the Iosipescu geometry.

1 INTRODUCTION

Finite Fracture Mechanics (FFM) has emerged as a reliable approach to determine failure load in many problems [1,2]. In the particular case of adhesive joints with composite materials, the use of FFM requires, among other mechanical properties, the strength values associated to the potential failure paths. Some of these failure paths involve bimaterial interfaces [3], as shown in Figure 1 (paths b and c).

The main drawback of the experimental determination of the interface strengths is that the abrupt change in mechanical properties in the interface gives rise to unbounded stresses. This non uniform stress state with stress singularities at the free edges avoids the identification of a nominal stress value at the instant of sample failure.

The geometry of the typical tensile and shear test samples have to be revised to achieve the most uniform stress state in tension and shear. This is the main objective of this study.

In Section 2, the definition of the modified geometries, avoiding the stress singularities, is addressed for the tensile and shear (Iosipescu) tests. In Section 3 the tests performed and the results are shown and discussed. In Section 4, some conclusions and final remarks are addressed.

Figure 1: Potential paths in the failure of an adhesive joint.

2 DEFINITION OF TEST GEOMETRIES IN TENSION AND SHEAR

From the three potential failure paths shown in Figure 1, we will focus on paths “b” and “c” which contain bimaterial interfaces, being path “a” a standard isotropic homogeneous case which does not represent any difficulty in the determination of the tensile and shear strengths.

The first step to define singularity-stress-free samples is to define the local material configuration at the bimaterial interface between the composite material and the adhesive. For that end, a previous study of the same authors has been used [4] which allows the determination of the stress singularity orders in anisotropic multimaterial corners, see also [5] for a comprehensive review.

The asymptotic stress state at the bimaterial corner, using a polar coordinate system (r, θ) with the origin at the corner tip, can be defined by a series expansion with separate variables,

$$\sigma_{ij}(r, \theta) \approx K \cdot r^{-\lambda} f_{ij}(\theta) + \dots \quad (1)$$

where K is the Generalized Stress Intensity Factor (GSIF), λ is the order of stress singularity and $f_{ij}(\theta)$ is the characteristic angular shape function. When $r \rightarrow 0$ and $\lambda > 0$, the stresses become unbounded. In many cases, where only the asymptotic stress field is of interest, the series expansion is truncated with the terms containing singularity stress terms.

Any test sample geometry for tensile or shear tests (Iosipescu type) for the strength determination of the bimaterial interface, will include a free-edge bimaterial corner with composite and adhesive. The way to eliminate the stress singularity is to find the adequate corner configuration (local modification of the standard sample) giving rise to a negative value of λ . For that end, and assuming that machining is easier in the adhesive side, a bimaterial configuration in which the angle that the adhesive forms with the composite material (α) has been analyzed. Figure 2 shows the corner geometries and results for the order of stress singularities (λ) for the bimaterial configurations involving failure paths “b” and “c”. Figure 2a (2b) shows the bimaterial configuration for failure path “b” (“c”) in Figure 1.

Figure 2: Bimaterial corner configurations to remove the stress singularities.

When the fiber orientation at the interface is 0° (failure path “b”) the stress singularity vanishes for an adhesive solid angle $\alpha \geq 65^\circ$, whereas for the fiber orientation equal to 90° (failure path “c”) the stress singularity vanishes at $\alpha \geq 75^\circ$. For adhesive angles of 65° , in both cases, no stress singularities appear and for the sake of simplicity, all samples will be modified locally at the interface free-edge to have an adhesive angle of 65° .

Figure 3 shows the original and locally modified geometries for the tensile test and Figure 4 shows the original and modified geometries for the Iosipescu sample. In the case of the tensile test samples, the local modification of the bimaterial configuration was achieved by means of a circular machining (Figure 3a), whereas in the case of the Iosipescu samples, firstly, the main Iosipescu geometry was done and then the little rounded V-notch was performed (Figure 4a).

Figure 3: Modified (a) and original (a) configurations for the tensile test.

Figure 4: Modified (a) and original (a) configurations for the shear (Iosipescu) test.

Modification of the tensile test samples follows the original proposal by Lauke and Barroso [6] and the modification proposed for the Iosipescu sample is new. To check the effect that the local modification has on the shear stress field, a Finite Element Model (FEM) has been done. Load introduction in the FEM model was introduced following the recommendations in [7]. Figure 5 shows the global and detailed geometries and mesh of both the original and modified geometries of the Iosipescu configurations and Figure 6 shows the shear stress distribution along the interface for the original and modified configurations. It is clear how the stresses vanish for the modified configuration at the free-edges. The shear stress field is obviously non-constant, but uniform enough for a representative shear strength value to be obtained at the instant of failure.

Figure 5: Finite Element Models of the original and modified configurations for the shear test.

Figure 6: Finite Element Models of the original and modified configurations for the shear test.

3 TEST RESULTS

Tensile samples have been tested in a universal testing machine in tension at a cross-head speed of 2 mm/min. Load-displacement curves for tensile samples with the carbon fiber side at 0° (parallel to the load direction) are shown in Figure 7. In Figure 8 the curves for the case with the fiber direction at 90° (perpendicular to the load direction) are shown.

From the test performed, only the tensile strength, calculated as the failure load divided by the cross-sectional area of the sample has been evaluated. Both in the straight samples (without notch) and the modified samples (with notch) the cross-sectional area is the nominal one (thickness \times width) of the un-notched section. Table 1 shows the summary of tensile test results.

Shear samples have been tested using the Iosipescu device. Figures 9 and 10 show the load-displacement curves for the samples with the carbon fiber at 0° and 90° respectively. Similarly, as done in the tensile tests case, only the nominal shear strength has been evaluated, dividing the failure load by the nominal cross-sectional area of the samples at the reduced neck section of the Iosipescu samples, where the bimaterial interface is located. Table 2 shows the summary of shear test results.

Figure 7: Tensile tests for samples with the carbon fiber at 0°.

Figure 8: Tensile tests for samples with the carbon fiber at 90°.

Sample	Tensile strength (MPa)				Mean (Mpa)	Std. Dev. (MPa)	CV (%)
	1	2	3	4			
0° without notch	11.6	16.6	17.8	18.0	16.0	3.0	18.7
0° with notch	31.7	30.5	30.8	30.2	30.8	0.7	2.1
90° without notch	9.1	12.7	9.8	10.0	10.4	1.6	15.2
90° with notch	12.3	8.5	16.3	13.6	12.7 ⁽¹⁾	3.3	25.7

⁽¹⁾ Mean value removing test “With notch – 2” is 14.1 MPa.

Table 1: Summary of tensile test results.

Figure 9: Shear (Iosipescu) tests for samples with the carbon fiber at 0°.

Figure 10: Shear (Iosipescu) tests for samples with the carbon fiber at 90°.

Sample	Shear strength (MPa)				Mean (Mpa)	Std. Dev. (MPa)	CV (%)
	1	2	3	4			
0° without notch	31.9	33.3	32.2	32.4	32.5	0.59	1.8
0° with notch	31.7	24.9	31.2	23.4	27.8 ⁽¹⁾	4.28	15.4
90° without notch	28.0	30.4	28.6	30.6	29.4	1.3	4.4
90° with notch	31.1	23.9	30.3	30.6	30.7 ⁽²⁾	0.4	1.3

⁽¹⁾ Mean calculated removing samples “With notch – 2” and “With notch – 4” is 31.4 MPa.

⁽²⁾ Mean calculated removing sample “With notch – 2” which failed outside the interface.

Table 2: Summary of shear (Iosipescu) test results.

Tensile test results in Table 1 show that there is a clear effect in the failure load with the presence of the notch at the epoxy (adhesive) side. In the samples with the carbon fiber at 0° (failure path “b”), the presence of the notch increases the mean tensile strength value a 92% (in fact, the failure in the notched specimens does not occur just at the interface but a little bit inside the epoxy side), whereas in the case of the carbon fiber at 90° (failure path “c”) the tensile strength increment is 22% if all results are considered. This increment is higher, 35%, if test result corresponding to sample “With notch – 2” is not taken into account, as it shows a very different failure behavior with respect to the other notched samples (see Figure 8).

It is clear that the presence of the notch, which eliminates the local stress singularity, has an important influence on the failure load. The free-edges that appear in the tensile test samples do not appear in the local corner configuration of the adhesive joint in Figure 1. Thus, the tensile strength value obtained for the notched samples (mean value of 30.8 MPa) should be considered as the reference value.

On the contrary, in the shear tests, in both test configurations (with the fiber at 0° and 90°), there is not any clear evidence of failure load change when testing with and without the notch. First of all, it is necessary to clarify the apparent different behavior, mainly in displacements, at the beginning of the tests, in Figure 10, between samples with the notch and samples without the notch. This higher apparent compliance of the samples without notch is due to a clearance of the jigs which was not corrected until the tests of the samples with notch. The presence of this clearance does not affect the failure load of the samples.

In the shear tests with the carbon fiber at 0°, even though eliminating samples (with notch) 2 and 4, which failed at a lower load than samples 1 and 3, the mean shear strength does not change significantly (32.5 MPa without notch and 31.4 MPa with notch). Something similar occurs with the shear tests with the carbon fiber oriented at 90°, where only a slight increase in the shear strength appears, probably associated to the dispersion of the experimental tests, more than to a clear influence of the notch in the failure.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FINAL REMARKS

The original idea of Lauke and Barroso [6] to evaluate the tensile strength of bimaterial joints has been extended to shear tests (Iosipescu) to evaluate the apparent shear strength of bimaterial joints. In the present study, and in the framework of failure prediction of adhesive joints with composite materials, the tensile and shear strength of bimaterial joints have been obtained.

The free-edge stress singularities typically appearing in bimaterial samples have been removed by a proper machining of the local configuration of the corner, generating a small notch in the adhesive side at the interface. The correct angle of this little notch has been determined to eliminate the stress singularities and the samples have been manufactured accordingly. Finite Element Models have been performed to check the vanishing of the stress singularities.

Tensile tests have shown a strong influence of the notch on the failure load and consequently, on the tensile strength, almost multiplying by two the tensile strength in the case of the carbon fiber oriented parallel to the load direction (0°).

Shear (Iosipescu) tests, by the contrary, have not shown any clear influence of the notch in the shear strength, the failure load not being altered in a clear way.

It can be concluded that the correct tensile strength determination in bimaterial joints requires the presence of the notch, whereas in the shear strength determination, the presence of the stress singularity does not affect significantly the failure load value.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the help in manufacturing the samples to the student Pedro Emilio Romero and Bernd Lauke and Dietmar Krause from Leibniz-Institut für Polymerforschung Dresden (Germany) for the careful machining of the Iosipescu samples.

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